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Work Programme Description	Getting the interest of individuals from non-academic and topic related professional communities in providing objective feedback on redevelopment issues is generally difficult, but some of the work done in predecessor projects (see, for example, http://lasalle-oikodomos.blogspot.com) have reasonably succeeded. This project will continue to explore the most effective methods to engage individuals from all backgrounds in discussions on urban planning and housing developments. This deliverable will be a report that overviews our experiences on community development projects and provides examples of best practice. The report will be of value to any group wishing to engage local community members in their activities: other networks, academic institutions, housing and urban planning departments, and social organizations.				
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Document history

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2	2015-04-29	Leandro Madrazo (LA SALLE)	Review and editing
3	2016-09-30	Leandro Madrazo (LA SALLE)	Collecting reflections from WP3 partners about the best practices from other partners
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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents a selection of the best practices on community integration in which the OIKONET partners have participated. The cases have been provided mostly by partners from WP3 Community Participation, and some from WP4 Pedagogical Activities.

The projects are the following:

- “Urban Pockets: The hidden potential of urban pockets and community participation as an engine in revitalizing these spaces”, Tirana, Albania. Presented by Polis University, member of the sub-network Community Participation.
- “Public space regeneration of residential neighbourhood near the Niko Dovana stadium”, Durrës, Albania. Presented by Polis University, member of the sub-network Community Participation.
- “Environmental Design for Crime Prevention”, Riga, Latvia. Presented by the Faculty of Architecture and Urban Planning, Riga Technical University, member of the sub-network Housing Research.
- “Get Well City, an International Summer School”, Cēsis, Latvia. Presented by the Faculty of Architecture and Urban Planning, Riga Technical University, member of the sub-network Housing Research.
- “Living/Dwelling. Participatory action between students of architecture and the residents of Ilinden”, Skopje, Macedonia. Presented by the Faculty of Architecture, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University, member of the sub-network Community Participation.
- “Defining strategies to facilitate access to social housing in a medium-size city”, Rimini, Italy. Presented by Heriscap, member of the sub-network Community Participation.
- “Involving Tarwewijk. Urban regeneration of vulnerable neighbourhoods”, Rotterdam, The Netherlands. Presented by the Institute for Housing and Urban Development Studies, member of the sub-network Housing Research.
- “Housing sustainability at the edge of an industrial area”, Bratislava, Slovakia. Presented by the Faculty of Architecture, Slovak University of Technology, and member of the sub-network Pedagogical Activities.
- “Participatory process in "Tras Talleres": memory as a working tool”, San Juan, Puerto Rico. Presented by the School of Architecture, Polytechnic University of Puerto Rico, and member of the sub-network Pedagogical Activities.

The documented projects have been commented by other partners. This way, it has been possible to engage partners from different sub-networks in a joint reflection about community integration in planning.

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1 Purpose and target group

The ultimate goal of the work reported in this document is to share experiences in the field of community participation in planning, to identify methodologies and practices that can be extrapolated to other cases, and to facilitate the creation of collaboration spaces across the three OIKONET sub-networks: Housing Research, Pedagogical Activities and Community Participation. The contents of this report are also valuable to other scholars and community representatives working in the field of community action planning.

2.2 Contribution of partners

The contents of this report have been gathered by the WP8 leader, Johan Verbeke (KUL) and the document edited by Leandro Madrazo (LA SALLE). The reflections of members of the sub-network Community Participation have been collated by Leandro Madrazo (LA SALLE), as WP3 leader.

These partners have contributed to the report with a description of a best practice case:

- P3 FASTU- Faculty of Architecture, Slovak Technical University, Bratislava, Slovakia
- P8 IHS- Institute for Housing and Urban Development Studies, The Netherlands
- P10 UKIM- Faculty of Architecture, University "Ss. Cyril and Methodius", Macedonia
- P14 RTU- Faculty of Architecture and Urban Planning, Riga Technical University, Latvia
- P22 POLIS- Polis University, Albania
- P23 HERISCAPE- Heriscape, Italy
- P33 UPPR- School of Architecture, Polytechnic University of Puerto Rico

The following partners have contributed to this report, by commenting the best practices from other partners:

- P3 FASTU- Faculty of Architecture, Slovak Technical University, Bratislava, Slovakia
- P10 UKIM- Faculty of Architecture, University "Ss. Cyril and Methodius", Macedonia
- P11 OAPPCR- Ordine degli Architetti, Pianificatori, Paesaggisti e Conservatori della provincia di Rimini, Italy
- P21 SOSTRE CIVIC- Sostre Cívic, Spain
- P22 POLIS- Polis University, Albania
- P23 HERISCAPE- Heriscape, Italy
- P32 FAU- Facultad de Arquitectura y Urbanismo, Universidad de Chile
- P33 UPPR- School of Architecture, Polytechnic University of Puerto Rico

Their reflections are included at the end of each project description.

2.3 Relations to other activities in the project

The case studies reported in this document have enabled us to learn about community actions carried out by partners and disseminate them through the network. Sharing this collective experience constitutes the basis to establish procedures for an effective involvement of non-professionals in the decision making processes affecting the living environment in its multiple scales.

3 BEST PRACTICE CASES

The examples of best practices provided by partners are presented in this section. The description of the cases has been done using the template included in the Appendix. Furthermore, members of WP3 Community Participation provided their reflections and comments about the reported cases which are included in the last section of project case description.

3.1 “Urban Pockets: The hidden potential of urban pockets and community participation as an engine in revitalizing these spaces”, Tirana, Albania.

3.1.1 Partner

P22- Polis University, Albania

3.1.2 Actors/stakeholders involved

- Co-PLAN (non-profit organization) which acted as a key local counterpart of USAID for the project development.
- Tirana Municipality which provided the required infrastructure and setup the legal frameworks.
- Polis University which offered technical assistance to the municipality for the regeneration project. Students, with the support of Co-PLAN, were the main negotiators between the private sector, locals and the municipality.
- Citizens were involved in the public consultation during the design process. In most cases they offered goods, such as gravel, benches, tree, plants and other parks amenities in exchange for putting their logo in the public spaces. In other cases, they were willing to maintain the parks and to improve their facades with the help of the students.
- Despite not being a direct stakeholder, the media played major role in spreading the word to the entire public.
- International organizations such as IAAU, URBEGO, Goethe Institute.

3.1.3 Brief description of the case

This pilot project is part of a line of research that aims to create a methodology in the regeneration of public spaces (more precisely, spaces between buildings and informal areas to be upgraded) in close collaboration with the local community, with the aim of assisting communities in implementing new public place instruments in order to improve their public places.

Due to the informal and unplanned development that Tirana experienced after the 1990s a lot of empty pockets or urban gaps were left between buildings. With unclear ownership, these gaps quickly became dumping sites, shelters for the homeless or were transformed into informal parking lots by nearby residents. Located between buildings, these spaces are spread throughout the city’s urban fabric making them reachable within walking distance.

The area chosen for urban regeneration is one of the few free spaces in this residential neighbourhood characterized by densely built urban areas.

3.1.4 Implementation

3.1.4.1 Schedule

The following phases were followed when implementing the project:

- Field survey and analyses (September-November 2014)
 - o Data collecting from the municipality
 - o Data collecting from terrain analysis
 - o Training workshop for the internship students involved in the project
 - o Site visit in the project area
 - o Getting to know the locals and creating community groups
- Preparation of the presentation to the local community of the possible scenarios with the assistance of Tirana municipality experts and students from Polis University (November 2014)
- The creation of the final working group involving all potential actors
- Meetings and open debate with all stakeholders involved (November 2014)
- Final project proposal to be presented to the wider community (narrative + projects/maps) (12 December 2014)
- Public meeting and open debate (part 2)
- Final presentation of the finances involving (all actors and the community present) (23 December 2014)
- First phase of implementation (the urban garden) (25 January 2015)
- Open presentation of the first phase (30 January 2015)
- Second phase of implementation (February 13 – April 24 2015)
- Open presentation of the first phase

3.1.4.2 Relevant issues addressed

A community development project of public places has been successfully achieved in the city of Tirana. The purpose of the project was to upgrade public spaces, to strengthen the community and to make sure that the places would be maintained by all the community. The sites were chosen after a survey was done by Co-PLAN and POLIS University students.

The ultimate goal of the project was the creation of a platform where residents, professionals and local administrators could engage in a collaborative discussion about the creation of public space. Through this platform, residents would learn how to build a community, since simply being neighbours and living close to each other is not enough to make it. To help them in this community-building process, a five-step methodology was proposed:

3.1.4.3 Working process

Step 1 – Mapping. Mapping of the potential sites to be intervened and drawing a map of them. This task was done by the students and it was them who later decided in which site they would intervene. Two sites were identified and one of them selected to carry out the project. Most of identified sites were leftover spaces dominated by concrete, waste, pollution and mostly abandoned. The residents living nearby did not seem to care much about the spaces and their revitalization potential.

Through questionnaires and open discussions with residents, we realized their interest to collaborate with the municipality of Tirana and with Co-PLAN to transform these urban pockets into parks for the benefit of the neighbourhood. The interest shown by the residents was scored in the selection process to choose a site for the project. We received questionnaires for 6 areas from which 3 were selected to start a Master Plan together with the support of the municipality

of Tirana Municipality which prepared the legal frameworks and provided the professional teams to collaborate with the community.

Step 2 – *“Spying “on them.* Co-PLAN, together with the students, conducted several visits to the chosen sites. This was done over a period of 2-3 days, with no contact with the residents, only acting “under cover” as “spies”. Movements, interactions, usage of place, discussions, stop points and many other social and spatial elements were recorded by the students during this phase. This is the only way we could understand the true usage of the place and know exactly what to offer to the community beforehand.

Step 3 – *Getting to know residents.* Identifying people profiles (elderly, students, kids and mothers) and their position and roles in the community (leaders, care providers), was part of the process. The students started by giving a few presentations to residents to inform them of the project and gauge their reaction or interest level. At this point, when negotiations were starting between the private investors, municipality and the locals, everyone’s input was crucial.

Step 4– *Giving residents what they want or need.* After the presentations the students created potential scenarios of designing a place together with professionals (Co-PLAN, Polis University, Goethe Institute) and explained them to the residents through open air presentations. For this purpose, students brought laptops, posters, beamers (which would be supplied by Co-PLAN and Polis) to present the work and discuss the ideas with the citizens on the site. This was the longest phase since there was lots of trial and error in order to get the best result. Only after the residents and students agreed on the form of intervention could the implementation begin.

Step 5 – *Getting the word out.* Co-PLAN together with the students created a short film/documentary and a website for all neighbours interested in following the same steps to improve public places with some help from the municipality.

3.1.5 Results and further work

3.1.5.1 What were the main qualities of this project?

- Teaching and strengthening community values through inclusive design methods.
- Creating a user friendly manual to guide future community actions.
- Activities proposed for the renewed public spaces were decided in collaboration with the inhabitants.
- The community will become more aware of their role in the design and maintenance of public space. They will be motivated to improve and harmonize collectively owned facades after the adjacent public spaces have been upgraded. Homeowners recognized that the area became more attractive and as consequence, the value of their propriety would raise in the near future.
- The area is more accessible, as the system of mobility was re-arranged and urban furniture was installed.
- Shaded areas (by vegetation) were provided for place to be used throughout the day. Urban gardens were facilitated as well.
- Street lighting was improved to make public place safer during the night.

3.1.5.2 What were the benefits of involving the actors?

- The bureaucratic process of implementation of the project was simplified.

- Including different actors in the process will assure maintenance through all stages of the project. As neighbours felt part of the project, they were willing to contribute planting trees and flowers and maintaining the green areas.
- Being a pilot project, it helped the municipality to start a methodology which could be further developed in other projects.
- Higher trust levels were achieved between the community and local authorities.

3.1.5.3 What could be improved?

- Time should be dedicated to winning the trust of the community through all the phases of the project and especially during the first presentations.
- Communication with the local authorities.

3.1.5.4 What can other organizations intending to implement similar processes learn from this experience?

- There was a strong coordination between partners.
- The workshops enabled partners to work together to solve the main issues.
- It is important that all partners discuss/address matters in face-to-face meetings with the community.

3.1.6 Images

Figure 1. Image of the Tirana case

Figure 2. Discussion meeting in the Tirana case

Figure 3. Discussion meeting in the Tirana case

3.1.7 Reflections

The reflections provided by members of the sub-network Community Participation about this project are summarized next:

- It is fundamental to take into account the implementation phase in order to have a precise assessment of the land ownership and the constraints of the spaces identified.
- It would be interesting to implement a web-based platform (a sort of Geo Portal) where all the users can upload pictures and comments about the spaces identified. This activity could reinforce the awareness and help the construction of a collective sense of the city.
- The project “Urban Pockets” encompasses a methodological approach in a community planning. Each type of stakeholder has a clear role in the process of strengthening the community. The project emphasizes the importance of public space and its importance in regions undergoing a social and economic transformation.
- This community project shows that role of academia is fundamental to provide a methodological toolset which helps local authorities and citizens to collaborate.
- Community participation helps to transform derelict spaces in the city into meaningful places. Co-planning helps to increase the awareness of city dwellers about the value of public space.
- In order to improve communication with local authorities and to improve maintenance, an app for citizens to report maintenance problems could be useful. With such apps it would be possible for local authorities to provide quick solutions or suggestions for improvements.
- Involving children – as a sort of special citizen– and also schools in all the participatory processes would be useful. In fact, they are one of the most important users of public

spaces. As such, their point of view could be very useful as well as interesting and surprising. Also, it could contribute to educating them as future active participatory citizens.

3.2 “Public space regeneration of residential neighbourhood near Niko Dovana stadium”, Durrës, Albania

3.2.1 Partner

P22- Polis University, Albania

3.2.2 Actors/stakeholders involved

- PLGP (Planning and Local Governance Project) assisted the Albanian Government in the implementation of the Law of Territorial Planning.
- USAID (U.S. Government Agency) financed the project.
- Co-PLAN (non-profit organization) acted as a key local counterpart of USAID for the project development.
- AKPT (National Agency of Territorial Planning) were implementers of the Durrës project as part of “Urban Renewal Projects - from design to city transformation projects” whose aim is to help local government (in this case the municipality of Durrës) to develop and implement new land management instruments established by the new Territorial Planning Law.
- The municipality of Durrës prepared all the necessary project materials.
- POLIS University offered technical assistance to the municipality for the regeneration project.
- The local community (the inhabitants of the area) were involved in the public hearings during the design process.

3.2.3 Brief description of the case

This pilot project is part of a line of research that aims to create a methodology in the regeneration of public spaces, encompassing formal and informal spaces, in close collaboration with the local community, with the aim of assisting municipalities to implement new land management instruments established by the new Territorial Planning Law. The area to regenerate represents one of the few free spaces in a residential neighbourhood which is very close to a huge informal settlement.

3.2.4 Implementation

3.2.4.1 Schedule

The following phases were followed when implementing the project:

- Field survey and analyses (1–19 September 2014)
 - o Gathering information from the municipality
 - o Site visit to the area
 - o Discussion on the analyses that municipalities presented to the mayor.
 - o Preparation of the presentation of the case study by the municipality of Durrës with the assistance of AKPT and the Polis University (19-29 September 2014)
- Presentation of the case study of Durrës in the “Urban Renewal Projects - from design to city transformation projects” conference (30 September 2014)
- Professional debate: Mayors Forum Workshop (30 September 2014)
- First draft (narrative + projects/maps) (12 October 2014)
- Public hearing (25 October 2014)

- Workshop/ meeting Polis University with AKPT and the Municipality (25 November 2014)
- Final draft (narrative + projects/maps) (16 December 2014)
- Workshop/ meeting Polis University with AKPT and the Municipality (December 16 2014)
- Final projects (Polis University role ends up with the design of the final project)
- Application for funding

3.2.4.2 Relevant issues addressed

- A space for the neighbourhood or a new centrality between the formal and informal city

This case study deals with the regeneration of public space in a neighbourhood in the periphery of Durrës, close to a huge informal settlement, consisting of low-quality residential blocks built after the after 1990s. Most of the free spaces between the blocks were occupied by houses which were in process of legalization. The same situation existed in the informal settlement, where there was a complete lack of free space. Considering the close connection between the urban area to be regenerated and the informal settlement, it was considered that the renovated spaces could help to attract the population of the informal areas. This way, it would be possible to promote the integration between local and incoming population. At the outset, two conflicting interests arose: to make the renovated area a central part of city, which could contribute to revitalize the surroundings; or to keep as a calmed, private area as residents preferred. These confronting views were at the centre of the discussions during the public consultation.

- Existence of private property

Part of the project area is private property. The draft urban plan (approval of which is still in process) contemplates the provision of green spaces. The main issue is how to find the most appropriate land management tool in order to transform private land into public space, while incurring as low a cost as possible for the municipality. Different instruments have been analysed and compared, such as expropriation and change of ownership.

- The flooding problem

One of the main problems pointed out by the residents was the flooding which can affect large areas. Although it is not our task to fully resolve the problem of flooding, it was a significant element to take into consideration.

3.2.4.3 Working process

Polis University was involved in this project with Co-PLAN which acted as a key local counterpart of USAID for the project development.

The first step was the collection of information from the municipality including maps, regulatory plans, cadastral maps and ownership status, demographic data, etc. Then, a working group with representatives from the municipality, AKPT and Polis University organized a site visit to the area. This was the starting point for a survey of the existing situation, which was further developed by the municipality. A meeting was held at AKPT to discuss the main issues at stake. As a result of this debate, a presentation of the case study was prepared which would later be delivered by the municipality in the Conference “Urban Renewal Projects - from design to city transformation projects”, which concluded with a round table debate (Mayors Forum Workshop). In this meeting, guest experts (from Albania and abroad) discussed solutions for the main issues.

Taking into account the various contributions, the municipality together with Polis University drew up the first draft of the project, which was later presented to the community in a public hearing which was organized in the municipality. After this meeting and public debate, some of the comments were incorporated into the design of the final project draft.

Polis University provided technical support not only in the design process but also in the analysis of the land instruments to implement the project. Different alternatives were proposed and compared by university experts. Then, it was the task of the municipality to choose the most suitable option. In this phase, AKPT supported the university with experts who provided legal advice to interpret the Territorial Planning Law in order to facilitate mechanisms to change the privately owned land into public space, something which could only be done with the cooperation of the administration.

Once the ownership problems were resolved, the design project was completed and a draft was presented to a group made up of experts from the municipality, Polis University and AKPT. The final comments from this meeting were reflected in the final project. The role of Polis University was to complete the process by proposing the design of the final project. The municipality is currently applying to USAID for funds to implementing it.

3.2.5 Results and further work

3.2.5.1 What were the main qualities of this project?

- As it was originally planned, this area was meant to be a network of public activities (sports and procreative) which created a new central hub for this part of the city, which is far from the city centre.
- The usages of the renovated public spaces were defined in agreement with the residents.
- The community will become more aware of their role in the design and maintenance of public space. They will be motivated to improve and harmonize collectively owned facades after the adjacent public spaces have been upgraded.
- The area became more attractive and as consequence, the value of their propriety would raise in the near future
- The flooding risk is minimized thanks to the proposed rain gardens.
- Car mobility and parking lots will not interfere with the kindergarten to assure children's safety. The number of parking places will increase slightly.
- The area is more accessible, as the system of mobility has been re-arranged.
- Shaded areas (by vegetation) were provided for place to be used throughout the day.
- Street lighting was improved to make public place safer during the night.

3.2.5.2 What were the benefits of involving the actors?

- The bureaucratic process of the implementation of the project was simplified.
- Being a pilot project, it helped the municipality to start a methodology which could be further developed in other projects.
- It was a project undertaken with the consent of the community, in so far as they expressed the willingness to contribute by planting trees and flowers and maintaining the green areas.

3.2.5.3 What could be improved?

- Public hearings could be organized in different locations in order to improve citizen participation. People, sometimes feel intimidated when they enter a municipal building.
- To organize workshops with children, because they are the main users of the space. Furthermore, they are not usually present in public meetings.
- During the meetings and the design process the municipality should involve engineers, not only architects and urban planners.

3.2.5.4 What can other organizations intending to implement similar processes learn from this experience?

- There was a strong coordination between partners.
- The workshops enabled partners to work together to solve the main issues.

3.2.6 Images

Figure 4. Durrës site

Figure 5. Durrës site.

Figure 6. Mayor's Forum

Figure 7. Mayor's Forum

Figure 8. Public hearing. Meeting with the community.

Figure 9. Public hearing. Meeting with the community.

3.2.7 Reflections

The reflections provided by members of the sub-network Community Participation about this project are summarized below:

- It is a well-structured action, with representatives of many different stakeholders and shareholders. Yet, it is fundamental to solve the land ownership aspect, especially in the case of a possible replication of the action. In fact, there is a need for a legal framework for the action, which could be provided by special legislation that enables residents to claim the leftover land from the public authorities.
- The connection with the municipality, local community and the city planning instruments has led to great progress in urban management and it has facilitated the achievement of the project goals. In this regard, this project can be a model for further actions.
- The aim of the project was to create a methodology for the regeneration of public spaces, encompassing formal and informal areas, by involving private, public, academic and community stakeholders. This methodology could be useful to assist municipalities implementing new land management instruments. More information on the results of the participatory processes might have been beneficial.

3.3 “Environmental Design for Crime Prevention”, Riga, Latvia

3.3.1 Partner

P14- Riga Technical University, Latvia

3.3.2 Actors/stakeholders involved

- Society “Pro-Police Latvia”, as initiator
- Riga Technical University, as supporting institution (teams of students and professors)
- State police of Latvia, as partner institution
- Representatives from planning departments of Riga municipality, as discussion participants
- CPTED experts, as invited guest lecturers

3.3.3 Description of the case

The area chosen for the project is a former cemetery, which is currently used as a park. The quality of the public open space is low; at the same time, it is used intensively for different activities. There is a need for both aesthetical improvement and increased security in this public space.

3.3.4 Implementation

3.3.4.1 Schedule

- Spring 2014:
 - April 08: Introductory lecture, site analysis
 - April 17: Consultation
 - April 23: Submission of the preliminary design, site plan, conceptual visualisations, details, schemes, workshop
 - April 24: Workshop
 - April 25: Workshop, submission/presentation of the final design
 - June 05: Opening of the exhibition
- Summer 2014-Winter 2015: Arranging the exhibition in several public places
- Winter-Spring 2015:
 - February 27: Stakeholders’ meeting, discussion about actions to take in order to put the best students’ ideas in practice, student presentations.
 - April 09: Meeting regarding planning activities for the Big Clean-up Day
 - April 25: The clean-up of the site
- Currently: There is an ongoing discussion in progress about the next activities, about how to implement the best students’ ideas in real life, how to find possible collaboration models.

3.3.4.2 Relevant issues addressed

The task was to create an environmental/urban design proposal for the area of Myra Street, in order to:

- Improve the safety of the public space
- Create a pleasant and safe environment for all social groups
- Provide pedestrian spaces, children playgrounds, parking spaces, public transport stops, bicycle tracks, leisure spaces, street lighting, etc.

3.3.4.3 Working process

Students had the task of designing a proposal for the improvement of the safety of an area in Riga, the capital city of Latvia, by using architectural and spatial design methods. The activity started with visiting the site and interviewing the residents. Then students received an introductory lecture by foreign experts in CPTED (Crime Prevention through Environmental Design), as well as representatives from the state police. Their proposals were shown in an exhibition which was open to the public.

3.3.5 Results and further work

3.3.5.1 What were the main qualities of this project?

- It was a pioneering project in Latvia; it was the first experience for all local stakeholders in CPTED (Crime Prevention through Environmental Design)
- Representatives of different sectors contributed to create the climate for interdisciplinary cooperation
- It gave rise to a large amount of quality, creative proposals to refurbish the selected area

3.3.5.2 What were the benefits of involving the actors?

- Possibility to analyse the problem of safety in urban spaces from different perspectives, facilitating the exchange of experiences between police experts, designers and planners.
- To find a new approach in the improvement of the public space, using architectural principles to increase safety levels in public space.
- Starting a cooperation between police and higher education institutions

3.3.5.3 What could be improved?

- It is advisable to create wider awareness and hence achieve a greater response from local authorities

3.3.5.4 What can other organizations intending to implement similar processes learn from this experience?

- To be open to innovative projects, to look at the opportunities for cooperation with other sectors of the society from new perspectives

3.3.6 Images

- Area 1: Miera iela (Tallinas iela - Mēness iela)
- Area 2: Miera iela (Mēness iela - Senču iela)
- Area 3: Miera iela (Senču iela - Klusā iela, Kazarmu iela)
- Area 4: Klijānu iela (Klusā iela - Lakstīgalu iela)
- Area 5: Mazā Klijānu iela (Klusā iela - Brīvības iela)

Figure 10. Site is a former cemetery territory, currently used as a park

Figure 11. Students presenting their proposals for the improvement of the security in the site.

3.3.7 Reflections

The reflections provided by the members of the sub-network Community Participation about this project are summarized below:

- It is fundamental to distinguish between the perception of safety and the actual crime rate. Both are relevant and each demands different actions and projects. In particular, the perception of safety could be dealt with through some particular design arrangements. One of the main general premises for a design for safety is to expose interactions between people avoiding “opaque” or blind views, for example, bushes, dense vegetable screens and walls in a park. This is particularly relevant for this case.
- Community participation is an essential component of good planning, because it enables the involvement of the beneficiaries of the area in question. The topic of environmental design for crime prevention in Riga brings to light a critical issue of social sustainability in the community. A topic that could be explored even in the case of Tirana, in areas that have undergone rapid urban development while the infrastructure and the use of space do not respond to the conditions required to create a safe and secure place. It should also be highlighted that the collaboration of the students with the respective actors such as the CPTED was very good. This case can help to furnish a methodology to increase the safety of public spaces using aesthetical improvements.
- The design could have followed a process which was more focused on the generation of materials produced by the citizens to increase community participation and integration. In this case, the structure of the activity could consist of the following phases:
 - Building a team: The team includes members of the target community, local authorities, academics and support professionals);

- Rough mapping: Meetings with the local community leaders and city officials to “rough map” the settlement, identifying real problems and issues to address. This would help to prepare a questionnaire;
 - Data collection: it should be performed in the presence of land rights holders and local officials in the field;
 - Spatial data/Design tools: they can then be linked to the person’s data using a spatial tenure relationship;
 - Reporting back: the results of the design process should be presented to the community at a validation event.
- Reprogramming and transforming public space is a relevant topic in transitional societies. This case presents architecture as a tool to improve dis-functional and derelict public spaces. The project is a good example of interaction of academia with public authorities. They became aware of the importance of experts and professionals in the pedagogical process of learning architecture. The meetings between students and stakeholders and the presentations delivered enables us to put the best students’ ideas in practice.
 - The close collaboration between students and foreign experts in CPTED as well with the representatives from the state police gives rise to unique opportunities to define a precise and meaningful methodology. Particular collaborations in which state police representatives educate residents to adopt safety measures regarding the public space could also be initiated.
 - The interaction in this case is very important; it is a productive instrument to understand the real role of a public space and its urgency.

3.4 “Get Well City, International Summer School”, Cēsis, Latvia

3.4.1 Partner

P14- Riga Technical University, Latvia

3.4.2 Actors/stakeholders involved

- Riga Technical University, Derived Public Person, Organizer;
- FOLD, NGO, General Manager;
- Municipality of Cēsis, Local Government, Partner;
- Rucka artist residency, NGO, Partner;
- International Team of Students, Participants;
- International team of tutors and lecturers;
- Local Residents, Guests of the Town, Involved Persons;
- Supporters — local businesses.

3.4.3 Brief description of the case

The aim of the summer school was to find solutions to unite the local community and to strengthen local identity in the town of Cēsis. Studies focused on social and economic issues in the municipality. The activities carried out were public lectures held by guest lecturers, interviews of local residents, development of design proposals by students in order to find ways to improve the public space quality, as well as the construction of full-scale installations.

3.4.4 Implementation

3.4.4.1 Schedule

It was implemented in the period July 26 – August 9, 2014

3.4.4.2 Relevant issues addressed

The “Get Well City” summer School took place in Cēsis— a town where health and leisure have always been intrinsic to the local lifestyle. Cēsis is located within the Gauja National Park, which is the largest protected natural area in Latvia. Its high biological diversity, varied terrain and natural water resources provide for outdoor sports of all seasons and traditional picking of mushrooms, berries and medicinal plants. In the early 19th century, local doctors contributed to the revival of water procedures in Europe by opening several hydrotherapy establishments. The healing qualities of natural springs have attracted countless visitors ever since and are still an essential part of the town’s identity.

What can rural towns offer to improve the well-being of their residents and visitors? Is clean air, local food and a stress-free working day a sufficient foundation for a healthy life in the 21st century? The summer school revisited local natural assets, infrastructure and traditions of wellness, proposed ways how they can be updated, and explored the relationship between the residents of Cēsis and the natural surroundings.

3.4.4.3 Working process

During the course, work was organised in several thematic studios, each employing a different approach to research and design. Some of the units focused on examining the physical, socio-economic and political realities of Cēsis at an urban scale, while others were dedicated to design, test and build ephemeral installations in the public realm, applying architectural and design methods. Students had an opportunity to work hands-on creating events and spatial structures to facilitate public interactions. The projects completed during the course became a

valuable contribution to the students' portfolios.

The local municipality financially supported the Summer School and suggested topics and sites to work on. For the city of Cēsis it was a chance to collect fresh ideas and discover new territories and directions for future development. Results of the Summer School were presented to the local public and authorities, and received wide publicity.

Local businesses, organisations and residents were selected by the students and tutors and invited to take part in the project— e.g. conducting interviews; researching sites, traditions and materials; building spatial structures and organising events. Examples of a successful collaboration included building Story Tower, a book exchange pavilion that is being looked after by Cēsis Central library, and Sālsmaize, an event organised to draw attention to the opening of Art Space Mala.

3.4.5 Results and further work

3.4.5.1 What were the main qualities of this project?

The Summer School offered the participants a unique opportunity to experience a whole project cycle in just two weeks — from the first sketches to model building to construction work in full scale and finally having the structures being used by the public. For a small town like Cēsis, the Summer School brought a lively buzz and a refreshing view on the city's qualities.

3.4.5.2 What were the benefits of involving the actors?

The results of Summer School become meaningful when the local municipality and people are involved in the process — the participants learned to deal with real issues and come up with real solutions, the town could gather valuable ideas and receive international attention — in contradistinction to a theoretical academic exercise.

3.4.5.3 What could be improved?

The course would benefit from a stronger publicity campaign. This would help to involve even more residents in the public event programme, attract more qualified participants, reach better results, and gain a higher recognition worldwide.

3.4.5.4 What can other organizations intending to implement similar processes learn from this experience?

Finding genuinely interested local actors to collaborate with, and making sure the food is great every day.

3.4.6 Images

More information can be found at <http://rtusummerschool.lv/>

Figure 12. Students working on the “Get Well City” case

Figure 13. One outcome of the Summer School

3.4.7 Reflections

The reflections provided by members of the sub-network Community Participation about this project are summarized next:

- The aim of the action was “to find solutions to unite the local community and to strengthen local identity”. However, the activities were series of lectures, interviews and development of design proposals.
- The case highlights the social and economic values of Cēsis and makes citizens and local authorities aware of them. The “installations in the public realm” and the structures and events to attract the public are inspiring.

3.5 “Living/Dwelling-Participatory action between students of architecture and the residents of Ilinden”, Skopje, Macedonia

3.5.1 Partner

P10- Faculty of Architecture, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University, Macedonia

3.5.2 Actors/stakeholders involved

- Faculty of Architecture, University Ss. Cyril and Methodius in Skopje, and Municipality of Ilinden. The Faculty of Architecture provided a team of 4 tutors and a group of 10 students from the ninth semester at Faculty of Architecture (Pedagogical team: Prof. Minas Bakalchev, PhD., Assist. Prof. Ognen Marina, PhD., Assist. Prof. Mihajlo Zinoski, PhD. Assistant Tasic Sasa, MSc.).
- The municipality of Ilinden participated with the representatives of the local administration, mainly from urban planning offices and with residents of the municipality.

3.5.3 Brief description of the case

As one of the fast growing suburban areas of the city of Skopje, the municipality of Ilinden has developed specific urban living and dwelling patterns that could serve as a sustainable model for the future development of the city. The participation of the residents is of great importance in achieving social sustainability of the future development.

3.5.4 Implementation

3.5.4.1 Schedule

The action was organized as a six-day workshop which encompassed direct contact with residents, conversations with the local administration and design tasks at the Faculty of Architecture. The workshop schedule was the following:

- Day 1: Introduction of the workshop program, objectives and tasks. Visit to the site and to the municipality of Ilinden. Communication with local residents.
- Day 2: Exploration of the site. Questionnaire distribution and interviews held with residents and representatives from the municipality.
- Day 3: Design workshop. Visiting lecture.
- Day 4: Design workshop.
- Day 5: Design workshop. Preparation of the final presentation.
- Day 6: Presentation of the results of the workshop. Design workshop critics.

3.5.4.2 Relevant issues addressed

In order to act critically, architecture must transgress and displace the political, social, economic, cultural and aesthetical condition of the time. Architecture has the possibility of not just representing, but transforming and being critical of these socio-political conditions. The objective of the workshop was to create a participatory action between students from the Faculty of Architecture and residents from the neighbourhood in the municipality of Ilinden. Students have investigated the actual dwelling and living patterns of the neighbourhood through the use of a comprehensive methodology consisting of mappings and interviews. The work has been done in close cooperation and interaction with citizens and local administration. The case study has been a residential urban block in Ilinden.

3.5.4.3 Working process

Information and data was exchanged among the main stakeholders. The students performed an analytical survey of the morphology of the residential buildings and compared it with the mapped patterns of living and dwelling in the local community. The gathered data was used for a comprehensive analysis of the potential for future urban sustainable development. Representatives of local municipality were involved in a participative process which was important to promote social sustainability of the urban growth policies.

3.5.5 Results and further work

3.5.5.1 What were the main qualities of this project?

The participants of the workshop have fulfilled the following tasks and objectives of the workshop:

- Preparation of a questionnaire to find out the social and spatial distinctive qualities of the place.
- Residents have provided their own statements reflecting their perception of the neighbourhood by answering the questionnaire;
- Students summarized the results and created “sociograms” from the answers collected in the questionnaire;
- Students presented the results to the representatives from the municipality of “Ilinden”.

3.5.5.2 What are the benefits of involving the actors?

- Students discovered the social patterns of inhabitants in relationship to their forms of dwelling;
- Residents have been actively involved in the creation of a specific identity of the local community and have been asked to describe it.
- Representatives from the municipality have been informed of residents’ needs and have actively negotiated possible solutions.

3.5.5.3 What could be improved?

- The collection of data and information.
- The methodology to facilitate citizen’s participation.
- The interaction with the local administration.

3.5.5.4 What can other organizations intending to implement similar processes learn from this experience?

- The preparatory activities related to the collection of data are important to understand the processes of urban growth and transformation in a particular area or community.
- The methodology of interaction and collaboration with local residents must be sensitive to the context.
- The capacity that local administration has to bring about collaboration and interaction with local residents through participative actions.

3.5.6 Images

Figure 14. Local neighbourhood in Municipality of Ilinden

GENERAL QUESTIONNAIRE

1. STATISTICAL PARAMETERS: FAMILY NAME _____

- Number of members in one household _____
- Useable living area of the house _____
- When is the house build? _____ Has there been an extension of the house? _____
- Is the house built according to the: architectural plan / traditional way
- Manner of parking the vehicle:
 - a) parallel to the street b) in the yard c) in a garage/overhang d) in a garage that is part of the house
- Type of family house by the number of free sides:

a) individual house

b) attached house

c) house in a row

d) four attached houses

e) atrium house
- The placement of the yard:

a) front yard

b) back yard

c) central yard

d) corner yard

e) side yard
- Does the yard have enough sunlight exposure for most of the daytime _____

2. PROGRAM AND SPATIAL PATTERNS

- Number of floors of the house _____
- Number of rooms on each floor _____
- Construction type :

a) massive

b) frame construction
- Materiality: concrete / brick / steel / wood
- Is there a :

a) balcony

b) terrace

c) loggia
- Are there vertical communications : indoors / outdoors
- The placement of the front door : central/ peripheral/ hidden
- Type of rooms in the house:

basement/ windbreak/ entrance hall/ hallway/ cloakroom/ toilet/ bathroom/ living room/ dining room/ kitchen/ bedroom/ children's room/ an attic
- In the yard, are there :

garage / summer kitchen / workshop / pantry

3. WHAT ARE THE NEEDS / PREFERENCES

- Is there a need for: a quest room, study room, library, toilet and bathroom for quests, relaxation room, dressing room, garage, garden, terrace with greenery
- Is there a need for more public, commercial content in the neighborhood? _____ Why / What kind? _____
- What else is missing in the way of living? _____
- Typology of forms :

a) square

b)rectangular

c)circular

d) L-form

e) U-form

f) T-form

g) Z-form

h) complex form

Figure 15. The template of the questionnaire used at the workshop

Figure 16. Map of usages of the semi-private zones

Figure 17. Sociogram of shared semi-private spaces

3.5.7 Reflections

The reflections provided by members of the sub-network Community Participation about this project are summarized below:

- A participatory action needs to not only be initiated, but continuously developed especially when the purpose is to increase the citizens' awareness of the achievements

of the action.

- The action was developed through a direct and transparent process, although in a quite conventional manner: analysis of the site, data collection, lectures on the topic, elaboration of the findings, development of proposals and the final presentation of results. The quality of the process is also manifested through the clear identification of potential further improvements.
- The action was accurately defined and planned. The working group assumed a mediator role between local authorities and residents. The clearer and more communicative the action plan, the more productive the result.
- This action was an academic exercise involving the municipality in a participatory process. This type of activities is very important to give students first-hand experience of the real problems that communities are facing and at the same time to show them the difficulties and the benefits of working with citizens. Participating in these activities during their studies helps students to decide if they would like to continue in this direction in their professional practice.

3.6 “Defining strategies to facilitate access to social housing in a medium-size city, Rimini, Italy

3.6.1 Partner

P23- Heriscape, Italy

3.6.2 Actors/stakeholders involved

- Municipality of Rimini: Social Housing Department - Department of the municipality that deals with the promotion and development of projects related to social policies, including social housing.
- Municipality of Rimini: Youth Policies Department - Department of the municipality that deals with the promotion and management of proposals and measures for young people aged 16 to 32 years.
- Municipality of Rimini: Urban Planning Department
- Carmi Bank Foundation (partner of Emilia-Romagna Social Housing Fund) – Bank foundation promoting the development and growth of social, economic, cultural and institutional areas of the territory in Rimini.
- Ordine Architetti Rimini (Chamber of Architects, Rimini) – professional board.
- Uni.Rimini - Consortium sustaining the University of Bologna at Rimini
- Acer Rimini (Affordable Housing Regional Agency) – Public economical body managing public affordable housing.
- Caritas - Pastoral Body of the CEI (Italian Episcopal Conference) promoting charity
- Papa Giovanni XXIII association - Catholic Associations working on poverty alleviation
- Slash Association - Student Association of Rimini
- San Giuseppe Foundation - Non-profit organisation working with orphans and single mothers
- Fratelli è possibile Cooperative - Organisation working on Social conflict mediation

3.6.2.1 Description of the case

The growing housing emergency has been affecting intermediate segments of the population in Italy (“grey area”) since the 1990s. This social group had previously been unaffected by such difficulties.

This part of population is unable to satisfy its housing needs on the free market due to either financial reasons or a lack of appropriate options on the supply side.

When it comes to policies, instruments and projects, social housing in Italy is characterized by the presence of many public and private institutions that operate at different levels addressing distinguished needs and targets. Although they try to offer different options to people in need of social housing, their responses often lack the levels of coordination and cooperation necessary to identify population demands, to define roles for each organisation and to establish a common policy to provide effective answers to the shortage of affordable housing.

The fragmentation of social housing policies, tools, projects and instruments, and the lack of collaboration between the public and private bodies dealing with social housing hinder the effectiveness of any action defined to give an answer to the housing needs of the “new” sectors (“grey area”) together with most disadvantaged sectors of the population.

When faced with the lack of public resources to sustain a social housing policy, the co-operation between individuals, associations, private bodies and institutions becomes necessary.

In this context, the purpose of the participatory action in Rimini was to involve community representatives of different segments of the population to define possible and feasible strategies to support solutions for the social housing problems in a medium-size city, like Rimini.

3.6.3 Implementation

3.6.3.1 Schedule

The participatory action in Rimini, which is one of the deliverable of *OIKONET work group 3* started in June 2014. The main activities were developed from November 2014 till March 2015. From March 2015 until the end of May 2015, some outcomes were completed.

3.6.3.2 Relevant issues addressed

The participatory action developed mainly gave participants the chance to identify difficulties and critical aspects in managing or developing projects of social housing in Rimini.

After interviewing the participants to outline Rimini housing situation, two round tables were organized to foster stakeholders' debate.

The discussion focused on the identification of four social housing projects and proposals coming from the actors involved in the activities.

The contribution they received from the round table was fundamental to the establishment of concrete actions and the creation of possible links to overcome the difficulties faced to develop the proposals.

Furthermore, the actors discussed the possibility of creating a permanent round table (possibly evolving into a steering committee) with the local associations and institutions involved in the action committed to facilitate access to housing and to assure the welfare of the population.

3.6.3.3 Working process

In the first stage of the implementation of the action, two researchers interviewed the actors. In the second stage two round tables participated.

3.6.4 Results and further work

3.6.4.1 What were the main qualities of this project?

The community representatives in Rimini were really active: their interest in the participatory process facilitated the development of the activities.

The municipality of Rimini often asks to have a precise picture of the housing situation reflecting all the sectors represented by the institutions, organisations and associations dealing with housing in Rimini, in order to strengthen the social public policy according to the real needs of the city. The round tables helped to work in this direction: the participants sharing their knowledge and experience came up with a methodological approach, which contributes to the local housing policy.

3.6.4.2 What were the benefits of involving the actors?

The planned meetings helped the representatives of the Rimini community to come up with strategies to create linkages with each other and work together to develop social housing projects.

By experiencing the discussion in the round table, the participants understood the importance of creating a network of institutions, associations and private bodies to meet the challenges of the shortage of social housing. Collaboration and integration of their aims helped to start developing effective projects to offer different options to solve the problem.

Furthermore, tighter future collaboration will help them to successfully apply for funding (e.g. usually private funds require big project, while the ones proposed from the third sector are too small in terms of quantity and dimension).

3.6.4.3 What could be improved?

The scope of the action is really complex and broad. As a guideline for similar experiences, it is important to define from the start how the stakeholders would continue to work on the proposals and actions they discussed in the meetings.

3.6.4.4 What can other organizations intending to implement similar processes learn from this experience?

In order to implement similar processes to the one in Rimini in other places, an awareness of the importance of the commitment of the participants is fundamental, because the effectiveness of the process depends on their responsibility and interest in the objectives.

Readiness and experience in mediation and coordination are required to take full advantage of the meetings and debates, thus avoiding to deviate from the project programme and to focus on the expected outcomes.

3.6.5 Images

Figure 18. Rimini, participant's interviews

Figure 19. Rimini, first round table on social housing

3.6.6 Reflections

The reflections provided by members of the sub-network Community Participation about this project are summarized below:

- The participation of policy makers and involved stakeholders is highly relevant and very important for the procurement of social housing for the specific and still emerging broad group of citizens (grey area).
- The participatory action is structured around two main activities: round tables and

interviews. The stakeholders involved are representative bodies and institutions working with the groups of citizens. It would be an added value for the future development of the participatory action to involve “users” in the round tables or through group workshops organized in the local community. Their involvement would further legitimize the process and would contribute to verifying the effectiveness of the adopted policies and actions from the user’s position.

3.7 “Involving Tarwewijk. Urban regeneration of vulnerable neighbourhoods”, Rotterdam, The Netherlands

3.7.1 Partner

P8- Institute for Housing and Urban Development Studies, The Netherlands

3.7.2 Actors/stakeholders involved

- Institute for Housing and Urban Development Studies (IHS) of the Erasmus University in Rotterdam.
- Municipality of Rotterdam
- Cultureel Denkwerk
- OVDB Tarwewijk (residence association Tarwewijk)
- Millinxparkhuis (community centre Tarwewijk)
- Thuis op Straat (neighbourhood watch)
- Residents of Tarwewijk

3.7.3 Description of the case

Tarwewijk is a neighbourhood in the South of Rotterdam with roughly 12,000 inhabitants. It is considered to be one of the 100 most vulnerable neighbourhoods in The Netherlands. It has the youngest population in Rotterdam with 60% of its population under 34 years old. It has a high rate of unemployment and a low safety index deriving mainly from drug related crime and domestic violence. The neighbourhood is ethnically diverse, with non-Dutch or English speaking inhabitants, making integration and neighbourhood cohesion a big challenge. It has a large housing stock mostly built before 1945, with parts of the 70% privately owned houses in bad condition, in need of major renovations and subjected to illegal sub-letting.

3.7.4 Implementation

3.7.4.1 Schedule

The workshop was an intensive 5-week work experience, where participants were to tackle complex issues such as inequality, segregation and neighbourhood decay in Tarwewijk. The period of implementation was from 16 February to 20 March 2015. The workshop allowed participants to tackle real issues by working in-situ on a project/case of relevance to the inhabitants of Tarwewijk, the city of Rotterdam and The Netherlands at large.

3.7.4.2 Relevant issues addressed

Tarwewijk derived its name from Tarwe (wheat) as it had been an area where wheat was loaded on/off the ships in the Rotterdam Maashaven (Maas Harbour) in the 1900's. Since then there has been a gradual but continuous exodus of middle income families and an influx of lower income families and short stay migrants in search of employment opportunities in Rotterdam; most of whom are attracted to the area for its cheap accommodation in mostly poorly maintained houses rented out by unethical landlords, regarded as “slum lords”. The landlords take advantage of the short stay migrant's unstable financial situation, illiteracy in Dutch and of the lack of social cohesion found in the neighbourhood which is principally due to the diverse ethnicities and cultures and the high housing turnover found in Tarwewijk. Tarwewijk's, unique factor also includes a high number of privately owned but poorly maintained housing stock, its proximity to the redeveloped highbrow neighbourhood of Kop van Zuid and the newly redeveloped creative hub neighbourhood of Katendrecht. Tarwewijk's proximity to the two

redeveloped neighbourhoods in Rotterdam has followed up on the social and economic restructuring of these areas, creating a sense of hope for some of the inhabitants of Tarwewijk, who long for a positive social and economic spill-over from the improved neighbourhoods, while others fear that the impact from Kop van Zuid and Katendrecht might bring new communities and activities that could exclude or even displace them from Tarwewijk.

3.7.4.3 Working process

The first week of the workshop were dedicated to collecting data on site, in the form of interviews, neighbourhood observations, expert's lectures and desk research. The second week entailed the critical analysis of the problems found in Tarwewijk based on six thematic areas, which included housing, public space, facilities and social programming, health, sports and wellbeing, employment and integrated planning. The third and fourth week involved participants setting objectives, developing and pre-testing the various strategies developed. During the fifth and final week, students finalized their work and presented their findings to all the stakeholders.

3.7.5 Results and further work

3.7.5.1 What were the main qualities of this project?

The project was result-driven; dealing with the improvement of a neighbourhood with real life people and problems, giving the participants a rare opportunity to work in collaboration with experts and practitioners in the field, with the prospect of having their ideas/solutions realized and improving a vulnerable neighbourhood.

3.7.5.2 Benefits of involving the actors

Involving various actors and stakeholders enabled the participants to see issues from diverse points of view and understand how an issue can be viewed as a problem to one actor but as an opportunity to another. It also challenged the participants to find cross-cutting and inclusive solutions to problems addressed.

3.7.5.3 What could be improved?

Access to the residents of Tarwewijk should be improved. A few of the residents were sceptical about the project, while others were unwilling to be interviewed. During the course of the workshop, more stakeholders operating in the neighbourhood showed up. They could have been involved in the early stages of the planning of the workshop.

3.7.5.4 What can other organizations intending to implement similar processes learn from this experience?

Interested organizations should be aware that working in neighbourhoods takes time to plan and execute. To ensure success in the project, local actors should be involved right from the planning stages to identify their needs and interest, to co-design of the project and to make contact with the inhabitants. It is also important to give these actors continuous feedback on the process and final outcome.

3.7.6 Images

Figure 20. Aerial View of Rotterdam Tarwewijk in February 2015

Figure 21. IHS Participants during the 5-week atelier in Tarwewijk.

3.7.7 Reflections

The reflections provided by members of the sub-network Community Participation about this project are summarized below:

- From a methodological point of view, the activity is well-structured and gives valuable hints about how a community could be involved in the design and planning process. In this case, community participation could be a tool for empowering people by ensuring the development of skills and the creation of employment opportunities while helping a community to renew its identity on the basis of its diversity.
- Working with communities in which the feeling of belonging is missing requires special efforts to engage people in a participatory process. To achieve this goal, it might help to set up a plan with long-term visions and actions with the following purposes:
 - Secure strong leadership: Built up a strong leadership with the support of key community representatives that support the initiatives and help to implement them.
 - Establish a formal structure: Develop a structure to provide support to the efforts of the community to change. Provide an overall strategic plan. Facilitate dialogue between partners. Managing data collection and analysis processes.
 - Engage diverse organisations, community leaders and residents: Engage stakeholders representing a broad spectrum of the community: young people, educators, health care providers, parents, and professionals.
 - Ensure true participation: Developing a sense of commitment and ownership of the proposed visions among the members of the community.
 - Ensure productive roles for young people: Engage young people in all phases of planning, development, implementation, and evaluation. Provide training to help developing youth-adult partnerships.
 - Provide a strategic plan/vision for the neighbourhood: Create a draft a strategic plan that puts forward the partnership's goals and objectives. A strategic plan is necessary to identify changes at the social and individual levels that will eventually lead to a reduction of crime and violence.
 - Education and training of the community: Training programs for the community by organizing forums, engaging local media, designing public service advertisements, using social media, and setting up round tables.
- This action was an academic exercise involving the municipality in the participatory process. It helps to highlight the importance of collaborating with citizens and municipalities in community development projects. The ways in which we communicate with residents, community organisations and planners is crucial to get a better understanding of the process and to get the best of all stakeholders involved.

3.8 “Housing sustainability at the edge of industry area”, Bratislava, Slovakia

3.8.1 Partner

P3- Faculty of Architecture, Slovak University of Technology, Slovakia

3.8.2 Actors/stakeholders involved

- Municipality of Bratislava
- Private developers
- Volkswagen
- FASTU teachers and students

3.8.3 Description of the case

This town-planning study addressed the communication with different stakeholders involved in the development of the western segment of the Bratislava city and in the area of automotive industry here. With 9900 employees, Volkswagen Slovakia is one of the biggest employers in Slovakia, as well as one of the biggest exporters. VW Bratislava factory has an area of 180 ha. Currently it produces Volkswagen Touareg, Audi Q7, Volkswagen up! ŠKODA Citigo, SEAT Mii cars as well as car body of the Porsche Cayenne. The construction of this plant gave a strong stimulus to the spatial development of the urban structure in this part of the city. However, the conflicting requirements of the city, automaker, developers and local citizens required harmonization. The extensive development of the new dwelling and shopping district and the intention to increase the car production with influence on traffic loads are in contrast with the efforts to improve the dwelling quality of local citizens

3.8.4 Implementation

3.8.4.1 Schedule

It was implemented from September 2013 to May 2014.

3.8.4.2 Relevant issues addressed

A research design studio identified the synergies brought about by the car industry in the city, the environmental impacts, and the requirements for sustainable housing design. The study was done in close cooperation with the municipalities of Bratislava and the city districts Devínska Nová Ves and Záhorská Bystrica, Volkswagen (VW) supported the study facilitating students the access to their facilities, providing counselling from their experts and helping to disseminate the results.

3.8.4.3 Working process

Representatives of the VW group, the municipality and private developers provided to FASTU students and teachers their visions about the development of the area. During the study, there were lectures and site visits in the area of VW plant. The final proposals were presented on a public exhibition with the participation of all the involved actors.

3.8.5 Results and further work

3.8.5.1 What were the main qualities of this project?

Research-based projects to find out solutions to actual urban development projects, directly working with the involved stakeholders.

3.8.5.2 What were the benefits of involving the actors?

They provided valuable information and insights which were incorporated in the proposals.

3.8.6 Images

3D MODEL NÄVRHU

3D MODEL OF DESIGN

Figure 22. FASTU design for the area development.

Figure 23. Public presentations of the research and designs with the attendance of actors involved in the area.

3.8.7 Reflections

The reflections provided by members of the sub-network Community Participation about this

project are summarized next:

- The case could benefit from including – or at least just identifying and simulating – a representation of the future dwellers in the process to express their expectations and needs.
- It is always very challenging to bring together citizens with corporations and developers in participatory processes for urban development. Firstly, because they tend to have opposite interests from the local community (citizens) due to the pressure of the capital, dominant economic interests and lack of interest in non-profitable development. However, most of the urban development that has occurred in the last two decades in Eastern Europe has been closely associated with the economic growth and with the economic interests of corporations and municipalities. So, this is a highly relevant process in order to understand the potential but also the problems that arise when the interests of citizens, municipalities and companies are at stake. The potential benefits of a development that seeks to satisfy these various interests are multiple. Hence it is highly recommended that this kind of development is addressed from a multidisciplinary perspective. The team must include experts in economic policies, environmental assessment of urban development, traffic and other relevant infrastructures. Then, synergies between this high level expertise and dwelling strategies must be explored in order to develop innovative and sustainable solutions to housing in areas dominated by the presence of industrial plants. The theme of this case study is very relevant for the future development of cities and a design studio is a good start to bring forward the relevant issues but the complexity of the problem supersedes what limits of the academic experience.

3.9 “Participatory process in Tras Talleres: memory as a working tool”, San Juan, Puerto Rico

3.9.1 Partner

P33- Polytechnic University of Puerto Rico

3.9.2 Actors/stakeholders involved

- Students from the Polytechnic University of Puerto Rico and from the University of Puerto Rico prepared the participatory process and the design proposal for the rehabilitation of the former railway bridge as a recreational public space
- Community of “Tras Talleres”, residents and future users of the recreational public space in the former railway bridge
- Professors Yara Maíte Colón and Omayra Rivera led the participatory process

3.9.3 Description of the case

At the boundaries of the neighbourhood "Tras Talleres" the former railway bridge is in a state of neglect. This structure is full of memories from the old train that existed in Puerto Rico and the workers who repaired the train in the “talleres” (workshops). The bridge will be restored and a participatory process was organised to make proposals for this renovation. These proposals should satisfy the needs of the residents while preserving the memory of the place.

3.9.4 Implementation

3.9.4.1 Schedule

It was implemented during five months, in a series of activities involving citizens, students and teachers.

3.9.4.2 Relevant issues addressed

The railway bridge has historical importance for Puerto Rico but also has symbolic importance for the residents of "Tras Talleres". However, many people were unaware of this and passed under it without realizing it. Therefore, it was necessary to emphasize the history of the bridge so that the residents realized of the importance of the rehabilitation.

3.9.4.3 Working process

The students prepared a participatory process that was represented as an interactive timeline. This line, made of small wooden rails, contained images and information about the history of the train in Puerto Rico. Between these images, residents placed cards which described their personal history of the place, that is to say, their oral history.

3.9.5 Results and further work

3.9.5.1 What were the main qualities of this project?

The visual resource used by the students encouraged residents to share their life stories and felt that these would be taken into account in the design of the rehabilitation of the historic structure.

3.9.5.2 What were the benefits of involving the actors?

The design proposal for the rehabilitation of the former railway bridge was based not only on the written history of the place but also in the oral history of the residents.

3.9.5.3 What could be improved?

The interactions with residents must be reproduced in different contexts to be able to engage more residents.

3.9.5.4 What can other organizations intending to implement similar processes learn from this experience?

Each participatory process is different since the culture of each place is different. The challenges is to discover the local conditions and to build on them.

3.9.6 Images

Figure 24. Participatory process in "Tras Talleres"

Figure 25. Participatory process in "Tras Talleres"

Figure 26. Proposal for the future of the site

3.9.7 Reflections

The reflections provided by members of the sub-network Community Participation about this project are summarized below:

- An interesting theme and focus, inspiring for others.
- This is a nice project and a good exercise for future architects. It is very important that students get to know real problems and try to find solutions taking into account the people who lived or have lived in the area they are planning. It shows that architects can apply their creativity to involve citizens in a joint reflection about the transformation of their living space.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The following guidelines, derived from the reported and analysed experiences, can inspire and help to develop a successful community integration project.

4.1.1 Concerning the design phase

It is fundamental to take into account the implementation phase as early as possible in a participatory process.

It is recommendable to develop a detailed mapping of the project site which includes a precise assessment of the land ownership and the constraints of the spaces identified.

It is crucial to specify the main goals and to envision the achievements of the participatory action right from the start. Also, it is important to provide an overall strategic plan at the beginning.

Meetings with community stakeholders are important to get them involved in the decision-making process. By formulating specific questions, students can become aware of the needs of citizens.

Before the implementation, it is important to have a good understanding of the legal framework for the participatory actions.

A participatory action needs to be accurately defined and planned.

Community participation can be used to carry out a critical revision of usages and meanings of public space.

Co-planning creates awareness of city dwellers about the value of public space and can specifically contribute to urban development.

4.1.2 Concerning the development phase

It works better when each of the stakeholders has a clear role in the process of community building.

Redefinition of public spaces can be of great importance in areas that need social and economic transformation.

Questionnaires addressed to residents can help to provide valuable information for developing a strategy for urban development. They can also be used to increase citizens' acceptance of the proposed design.

Higher education institutions can play a stimulating and positive role to foster community participation. Sharing experiences from other cases can improve the level of expertise as well as the experience of participants. Universities can play a stimulating role by proposing research issues and providing methods to guide the participatory planning actions. They can also play a role as mediators between local authorities and citizens.

It is fundamental to distinguish between the perception of safety and the actual crimes. Both are relevant, but each demands different actions and initiatives.

Sometimes, a more formal structuring of a participatory process helps to trigger change in the community.

4.1.3 Concerning the implementation phase

Apps could be used to improve communication with local authorities and citizens. They could become part of a platform to provide citizens with reports and other information, and as communication tool to suggest improvements or to bring new ideas for project development.

Involving children – as a sort of special citizen – and also their schools in a participatory process is recommendable. In fact, they are one of the important users of public spaces and their point of view can be useful and surprising. Also, it would contribute to educating them as future active citizens.

Likewise, it is also important to engage young people in all the phases of planning, development, implementation, and evaluation of community-led action plans. In this regard, training to develop youth-adult partnerships would be useful.

Participatory actions do not have to be circumscribed to a particular scale; they can encompass issues at various scales.

The design process needs to be re-oriented to include contributions made by community stakeholders (e.g. young people, educators, health care providers, parents, future dwellers and community-based organizations). With this aim, a participatory activity could be structured in the following way: 1. Building a team (the team includes members of the target community, local authorities, academics and support professionals); 2. A rough mapping (meetings with the local community leaders and city officials to “rough map” the settlement, identifying real problems and phenomena. This step would give a general sense of issues to be addressed and would inform the preparatory process of the questionnaire); 3. Data collection in the field performed in the presence of land rights holders and local officials; 4. Spatial data/Design Tools (these can be linked to the person’s data using a spatial tenure relationship); 5. Reporting back (the results of the design process should be presented to the community at a validation event); and 6. Reporting final results.

From an academic perspective, community action plans should develop following a straight and clear process: analysis of the site, data collection, lectures on the topic, analysis of the findings, development of proposals and final presentation of results.

Community participation can be a tool for empowering people, to help them to be actively involved in the process of building an identity for the community, of forging a sense of belonging.

4.1.4 Overall

A web-based platform could be a useful tool to implement some participatory activities. It could be a place where all users upload images and comments (as it is done in the digital environment of the JPI Incubators of Public Space project). Such platforms could reinforce the citizens’ awareness about city development.

Community participation is an essential component of good city planning because it ensures that urban developments will benefit specific stakeholders.

The interaction between community actors is necessary to help them to understand the value of public spaces.

Reprogramming and transforming a public space is particularly relevant in transitional societies. Architectural and urban designs can help to improve dis-functional and derelict public spaces.

Through their participation in community outreach projects, students become aware of the importance of bringing together experts and citizens in the design and planning process. A

close collaboration between students and experts offers an opportunity to positively transform existing pedagogical practices, particularly in the design studio.

A participatory action needs to be fostered and improved constantly, especially in order to increase citizens' awareness of the achievements.

The participation of policy makers and local stakeholders is highly relevant and very important for the procurement of social housing. Their involvement can help to legitimize the process and contribute to verify the effectiveness of the adopted policies and actions.

5 APPENDIX A: TEMPLATE

The following template was used to describe the best practice cases.

1 Case description:

- 1.1 Title of the project, partner
- 1.2 Actors/stakeholders involved (name of organization, type of actor, role; one line per organization)
- 1.3 5 Brief description of the case

2 Implementation

- 2.1 Schedule
- 2.2 Relevant issues addressed
- 2.3 Working process

3 Results and further work

- 3.1 What were the main qualities of this project?
- 3.2 What were the benefits of involving the actors?
- 3.3 What could be improved?
- 3.4 What can other organizations intending to implement similar processes learn from this experience?

- 4 **Images** (at least two figures, preferably one of the site and one of the activities)